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502. Turkish

- Lit.: Swift, Lloyd B.: A reference grammar of Modern Turkish (Uralic and Altaic Series Vol. 19), 1963
Lees, Robert B.: The phonology of modern standard Turkish (Uralic and Altaic Series Vol. 6), 1961
Lewis, G.C.: Turkish Grammar (1967)
Underhill, Robert: Turkish Grammar (1976)
Hayes, Bruce: Metrical stress theory (1995)

I. Segmental Properties

- Word-initially: all consonants allowed except /^hg/ - this is what Swift
- But Lewis adds: native words don't begin with /c,f,Ō,l,m,n,r,z/ - exception to this are interrogative particle /mi/, onomatopoeic words, /ne/ 'what'
 - ☐ Therefore /nicin/ is a compositum of /ne + icin/
 - ☐ I'm sorry, my mistake: *cocuk - begins with çocuk
- Clusters occur initially (word and syllable) only in words of recent western borrowing and in a few onomatopoeic words
- Clusters don't occur in conversational styles of spoken Turkish
- Finally:
 - ☐ don't occur: /b,d,c,^hg,g,÷/
 - ☐ clusters occur in **native** and loanwords
 - ☐ all final clusters as second member either a voiceless stop or a fricative
 - ☐ examples: /kám/ 'training camp'
 - /ként/ 'city'
 - /rénk/ 'colour'
 - /serp/ 'sprinkle'
 - /cílt/ 'volume'
 - /kesp/ 'acquisition'
 - /zév/ 'joy'
 - ☐ clusters consisting of voiced stop as first member and voiceless consonant as second are forbidden
 - but existing originally in some loanwords: devoicing of the first member but not when epenthesis of vowel
 - ex. zabit zabit-ta zapt-a 'seizure' (Lees)
 - ☐ only /z/ of the voiced fricatives occurs in final clusters
- medials: no restriction on clusters in the middle

- final voiced stops of certain base morphemes are devoiced if final and before consonants
- definition (Swift): " a base is a form in Turkish which contains more than one morpheme and which fulfils the conditions for membership in one of the two form classes, substantive or verb. Thus a base is a substantive or verb consisting of a root plus one or more suffixes."
- set of noun morphemes with final or preconsonantal /q/ or /k/ - lost before 3.poss-suffix

- a sequence of two vowels is reduced at morpheme boundary but not at word boundary or morpheme medially
 - each vowel is syllabic
 - epenthesis of vowel into final consonant cluster and in preconsonantal position
e.g. beyin vs. beyn-i 'his brain'
 - [?] I don't think it is a metathesis because the two /i/'s are of different origin
 - [?] In /beyin/ it is analysed by Lees as the epenthetic vowel
 - [?] In /beyn-i/ it is the morpheme for the third person possessive
 - [?] Depending on the grammar there are two analyses for this phenomenon
 - Lees – Epenthesis:
 - There are exceptions but generally Turkish base morphemes never show final consonant clusters unless followed immediately by a vowel initial morpheme
 - Small set of native Turkish nouns, almost exclusively body parts, in which final clusters only appear before vowels, ex. beyn-e 'brain (dative)';
qoyun qoyun-a (dative) 'sheep' qoyun qoyn-a 'chest'
 - Large set of borrowed bases showing the same alternation ex. bahis bahs-e 'discussion'
 - Vowel which appears between the two consonants when the cluster occurs before consonants or word boundaries is, with a small number of vowel-harmonic exceptions just the vowels subsumed under morphophoneme /I/ (ɪ, i)
 - Bases are considered to be consonant-cluster-final-morphemes
 - Swift – Vowel Loss:
 - Number of roots or bases with /i/, /ɪ/, /ü/, /u/ in the second syllable which exhibit alternates lacking this vowel under certain circumstances
 - Ex. isim / ism 'name'
/isim/ - in isolation or preceding suffixes with low vowel harmony (front / back – alternation between a and e in suffix)
/ism/ - before vowel-initial suffixes with high vowel harmony (front/ back in combination with high – alternate between i, ɪ, u, ü)
 - Vowel determines vowel in suffix, even when loss
ex. akis 'reflection' aks-i 'it's reflection', but normal vowel harmony would require aksɪ
 - Variation appears also when words of this group are compounded with et / ed- 'do, perform' or suffixed with non-harmonic suffix -en
 - Lexically conditioned
 - Two other instances of 'vowel loss':
 - Unstressable suffix –ra 'place' frequently occurs before relational suffixes –da, -dan, -(ya) in an alternate without the vowel
 - Certain substantive bases lose their final vowel before suffix -la
- arabic and persian loanwords violate the rule of vowel and consonant harmony
- loanwords in general fail to obey certain very general phonological rules: restriction on clustering and vowel and consonant harmony, but if there are morphemes suffixed, then these suffixes follow the rules

- Turcification process: insertion of a harmonically appropriate vowel between phonemes of stop-initial clusters and preceding /s/ - initial cluster
e.g. /psikoloji/ > /pisikoloji/
- ellipsis: reduction of vowel sequences at morpheme boundaries = progressive ellipsis which deletes a vowel following a vowel-final morpheme unless intervening juncture is that of a composite verb
- vowel harmony:
 - ☐ within word boundaries vowels of certain suffixes and native words are assimilated to preceding phonemes in respect to the feature of flatness and gravity
 - ☐ so long as it is confined to the sequence between word-boundaries this progressive assimilation leaps over morpheme juncture and intervening non-harmonic consonants as /s,m,t,y/
 - ☐ tendency of each succeeding syllabic in a word to be determined in its phonemic shape by the phonemic shape of the preceding
 - ☐ vast majority of native polysyllabic roots to exhibit vowel harmony internally
 - ☐ almost all suffixes have alternate forms in occurrence of certain vowels
 - ☐ parameters: front / back ; rounded / unrounded
 - ☐ so two kinds of assimilation: each harmonically suffix belongs to one or the other
- vowel loss in roots or bases with high vowels in second syllable in some circumstances
- vowel assimilation in compounds and ellision
e.g. né has an alternate n´ > nì:cin ,why´
- consonant harmony:
 - ☐ tendency for stops occurring on one side of a morpheme boundary to belong to the same voice class as the phoneme on the other side of the boundary
 - ☐ final consonant harmony: : with minor exceptions no words end in a voiced stop, also not in inflectional markers
- initial consonant loss: only in consonant initial suffixes after consonant final stem
e.g. -yim > -im
- final consonant loss: substantive bases, suffixes loses ,n´ before suffixes of possessed groups
- final liquid devoicing in word final position before a following consonant initial word or in absolute final
- glottal stop: optionallz before vowels and loss before consonants and word-finally
- initial voicing in suffixes – alternate between voiced and voiceless depending on stem-final consonant

- Simple word: single root with or without permitted suffixes and contains a single word stress

- syllabification: normally an intervocalic consonant goes with the following syllable, there are exceptions e.g. san-art
- permitted patterns of syllable: V / mevzu:ú / (letzte Silbe) ,it´s subject´
VC, VCC all three don´t occur initially
CV, CCVC, CVCC, CCVCC
- pattern of syllabification is automatic without regard to boundaries between morphemes or between words

- single consonants initially or between vowels are in syllable with following vowel
- two consonants occurring adjacent are split: first belongs to preceding, second to succeeding syllable
- three consonants in series: first two are generally a cluster belonging to the preceding, third to succeeding syllable
e.g. harp -te ,in war'
CVCC-CV
exceptions: recent loanwords where third intervocalic consonant is /r/
e.g. sür -priz ,surprise'
CVC-CCVC

II. Prosodic Properties

- primary stress in general on the final syllable in native words
- exceptions are often borrowings are stressed on some other syllable
- with addition of suffixes position of stressed syllable doesn't change in words, where stressed syllable is not the final
- Lees: in final stressed words position of stress is determined by succeeding syllable added:
 - ☐ if suffix can't be stressed, position of stress remains, otherwise stress is transformed to suffix
 - ☐ an unstressed suffix should be preceded by a stressed syllable even when this unstressed suffix is not the last
 - ☐ e.g. çocuk ,child', çocuklár ,children', çocuklarımız ,our children'
 - ☐ an unstressed suffix normally requires an immediately preceding primary stress
 - ☐ primary stress will always occur on the strong (=stressable) syllable immediately preceding the first weak syllable of the word, counting from the left or if there be none, on the final syllable
 - ex. giderémiyecekler mi? 'Won't they be able to remove it?'
Syllables: *II*III* (* weak, I strong)
 - gidereceklerí 'their removing of it'
syllables: *IIIII
 - ☐ negation, question particle are unstressable
 - ☐ p. 46 list of suffixes which contain at least one weak syllable
- each word has one primary stress
- alternative analysis by Barker (Hayes, 1995) :
 - ☐ right-to-left-iambic analysis
 - ☐ in subset words ending in heavy syllable-light syllable-syllable bear antepenultimate stress
 - ☐ words ending in light syllable-light syllable and heavy syllable are stressed on the penult
 - ☐ by marking the final syllable extra-metrically then creating a iamb at the right edge of the stress-domain
 - ☐ a penultimate light syllable is prevented from forming a foot on its own when it is preceded by a heavy syllable
- alternative analysis by Hayes (Hayes, 1995) :
 - ☐ invoke powerful extrametricality rules so that all final syllables are treated as light

☐ so that the same pattern can be derived with right-to-left moraic trochees with foot extrametricality in clash

- in ezafet groups accent is normally on the first element on the syllable which carries the accent when the word is spoken in isolation
- in compound verbs (noun + verb) the accent is on the last syllable of the first member
 - ☐ examples (Lewis): ba@ 'head', bakán 'minister' bá@bakan 'prime minister'
cıplák 'naked' cırılçıplak 'stark naked'
bir 'a', takım 'set' birtakım 'several'
 - ☐ ezafet: T'ürkiye Cumhuriyeti 'Republic of Turkey'
yemek odası 'dining room'

III. Morpho-Syntax

- exclusively suffixing
- concatenative, phonological bound morphemes, segmentable
- non-flexive
- results in complex synthetic words trigger some phonological and morphological adjustment
e.g. çocuk – un > çocu:n ,child – GEN'
- many suffixes vary in form whether they are attached to a consonant or to a vowel
- majority of morphemes have both free and bound morpheme alternate
e.g. base morpheme / kitap/, /kitab-/
 - free: kitáp
 - bound: kitap / kitab- - bound, since they occur only with suffixes
- minority, but of high frequency have only bound forms
- no non-adjacent allomorphy observed
- no infixation, simulfixation
- reduplication:
 - ☐ adjectives for emphasis: total
 - ☐ adverbs: total
 - ☐ examples (Swift): hemen 'soon, at once' hemen hemen 'almost' ; güle
'smiling' güle güle 'Good bye' ; sabah
'morning' sabah sabah 'early in the morning' Swift:
"properly not a single word but a phrase"
 - ☐ intense form of adjectives made by reduplication of first syllable
in connection with segment mutation: aç ık > apaç ık
,open'
yalnız > yapayalnız / yapyalnız
,only'
 - ☐ accent lies on the syllable preceding the stem
 - ☐ examples (Swift): ba@ká 'other' bámba@ka 'entirely different'
çür'ük 'rotten' ç'ümçürük 'entirely rotten'
tazé 'fresh' táptaze 'fresh as can be'
 - ☐ few words with more complex reduplication pattern, no rules cited
ex.(Swift) çplák 'naked' cırılçıplak 'entirely naked';
yalnız 'alone' yapáyalnız 'entirely alone'
 - ☐ first syllable is followed by a consonant: /m, p, r, s/ - choice is fixed and predictable to a very limited extent

- ☐ reduplicated syllable may not end with the same consonant as either the first or second of the adjective
 - ☐ not productive
 - ☐ usually a noun reduplicated with /m/ replacing the first consonant of the repetition
 - ☐ number of expressions looking like reduplication but without regular pattern new ones can be invented
 - e.g. çocuk çocuk ,household' (children and stuff)
- clitics and particles:
- ☐ ile: between conjuncts
 - can be suffixed on first conjunct by replacing /i/ by /y/ - loss after consonants
 - primary stress precedes
 - ☐ some occur as first element in clause – have a similar stress pattern in cases: first or second syllable, most on penult syllable
 - e.g. yalnız ,only' ; ama ,but'
 - ☐ conjunctives between clauses stand finally of the first clause
 - e.g. -ki - always unstressed
 - ☐ particle no vowel harmony if free standing
 - ☐ clitic ,mi' interrogates any structure to which it is attached, following the rules of vowel harmony
 - ☐ further clitics exhibiting vowel harmony: de ,too' , ise ,if it is'

VI. Other Questions

- reduction of unstressed vowels not mentioned
- word-word-combinations:
 - ☐ noun (without relational suffix) + verb base
 - e.g. kitap oku ,a book-read'
 - ☐ compound verbs: noun + verb base et- / ed- ,perform' or ver- ,give'
 - e.g. ispát et ,prove'
 - ☐ possessive compounds: noun (modifier) + noun (head) –with possessed suffix
 - e.g. ev kapısı house-door'
 - ☐ subject verbal compounds: Dep – noun without relational suffix
 - Head – verbal form (participle, verbal nominal, finite verbal predicate, subordinate clause verb form)
 - e.g. Alí gedi̇gi gün ,Ali, his having come day' / ,the day of Ali's coming'
 - ☐ juxtaposition: babaanne ,paternal grandmother
 - ☐ noun + noun + li: e.g. cin ,demon', fikir ,thought' > ciinfikirli ,shrewd'
 - ☐ adjective + noun + li: e.g. deli ,mad', kann ,blood' > delikanlı ,young man'
 - ☐ noun + adjective: süt ,milk', beyaz ,white' > sütbeyaz ,milk-white'
 - ☐ noun + 3rd person suffix + adjective: e.g. el-i ,his hand', aç ık ,open' > eliaçık ,generous'
 - ☐ noun + verb: e.g. kül ,ash', bastı ,it pressed' > külbastı ,grilled meat'
 - ☐ onomatopoeic word + verb: e.g. çit ,crack!', kırıldım ,I have been broken'
 - > çitkırıldım ,fragile, effeminate'
 - ☐ verb + verb: e.g. çakar ,it strikes fire', almaz ,it doesn't take' > çakaralmaz

,useless'

- no bipartite stems
- periphrastic morphology:
 - ☐ theoretically the separate forms like aliyor idim ,I was taking' instead of aliyordum might be expected (but only in past) but their use is in fact an Armenianism
 - ☐ negation: infinite verb + Aux
e.g. almakta deḡgilim ,I am not taking' (infinitive)
 - ☐ necessitative: verbstem-meli + Aux : only in past
e.g. gelmedi idim but also gelmeliydim ,I had to come / should have come'
 - ☐ Pluperfect, conditional: infinite verb + Aux
e.g. geldi idiysem but also geldim idiyse ,If I had come'
 - ☐ rarely used, when use is possible there exists an non – periphrastic alternative
- postpositions:
 - ☐ follow the noun
 - ☐ require certain case suffix on noun (nominative, genitive, ablative)
 - ☐ postpositional phrase accented according to compounding rules
 - ☐ few can appear as suffixes, but the majority are independent words